

Figure S1: Linkage disequilibrium (LD) analysis of SNPs in the study population. The number in the square represents LD coefficients. Red represents the highest LD coefficients. LD coefficients greater than 90 indicates linkage disequilibrium between the two SNPs. (A)-(E) LD block of SNPs of maternal *APOE*, *LDLR*, *LPL*, *PCSK9* and *SCARB1*, respectively. (F)-(J) LD block of SNPs of fetal *APOE*, *LDLR*, *LPL*, *PCSK9* and *SCARB1*, respectively.

Table S1 Primary information for SNPs of genes in maternal and UV blood

Genotyped SNPs	Chromo -some	Mutation	Reference Allele	Mutated allele	Rare allele	Maternal blood ^a			UV blood ^a		
						MAF in the MSPH	MAF in the MPH	P-value for HWE in the MPH	MAF in the MSPH	MAF in the MPH	P-value for HWE in the MPH
<i>APOE</i> rs157582	19	45396219	C	T	T	0.21	0.18	0.30	0.17	0.14	0.38
<i>APOE</i> rs429358	19	45411941	C	T	C	0.13	0.10	1.00	0.10	0.09	0.37
<i>APOE</i> rs440446	19	45409167	G	C	G	0.42	0.39	0.08	0.42	0.34	0.32
<i>APOE</i> rs7412	19	45412079	C	T	T	0.08	0.13	1.00	0.06	0.07	1.00
<i>APOE</i> rs769450	19	45410444	G	A	A	0.20	0.19	0.24	0.22	0.17	1.00
<i>LDLR</i> rs1003723	19	11224181	C	T	T	0.17	0.14	0.77	0.13	0.16	0.26
<i>LDLR</i> rs2569556	19	11218965	G	A	A	0.24	0.29	0.46	0.25	0.25	0.32
<i>LDLR</i> rs2738459	19	11238473	C	A	A	0.32	0.29	0.71	0.24	0.30	0.48
<i>LDLR</i> rs2738466	19	11242765	G	A	G	0.38	0.33	0.06	0.41	0.36	0.52
<i>LDLR</i> rs6413504	19	11241915	G	A	G	0.32	0.28	0.85	0.28	0.33	0.74
<i>LDLR</i> rs6511720	19	11202306	G	T	T	0.01	0.01	1.00	0.01	0.01	1.00
<i>LDLR</i> rs7258950	19	11250139	G	A	A	0.21	0.27	0.57	0.22	0.20	0.65
<i>LPL</i> rs12678919	8	19844222	G	A	G	0.09	0.10	1.00	0.10	0.10	1.00
<i>LPL</i> rs263	8	19812812	C	T	T	0.25	0.23	0.83	0.25	0.18	0.80
<i>LPL</i> rs268	8	19813529	G	A	0	0.00	0.00	1.00	0.00	0.00	1.00
<i>LPL</i> rs283	8	19815098	C	T	T	0.15	0.15	0.55	0.19	0.16	0.79
<i>LPL</i> rs320	8	19819077	G	T	G	0.22	0.21	0.03	0.22	0.19	0.63
<i>LPL</i> rs326	8	19819439	G	A	G	0.22	0.21	0.03	0.22	0.19	0.63
<i>LPL</i> rs328	8	19819724	G	C	G	0.09	0.11	1.00	0.10	0.10	1.00
<i>LPL</i> rs4406409	8	19868971	C	T	C	0.22	0.21	0.04	0.22	0.18	1.00

<i>PCSK9</i> rs10788994	1	55500976	C	T	C	0.36	0.37	0.87	0.39	0.37	1.00
<i>PCSK9</i> rs11206510	1	55496039	C	T	C	0.06	0.07	1.00	0.08	0.07	1.00
<i>PCSK9</i> rs11583723	1	55505926	C	T	T	0.11	0.12	0.08	0.13	0.11	0.48
<i>PCSK9</i> rs11591147	1	55505647	G	T	0	0.00	0.00	1.00	0.00	0.00	1.00
<i>PCSK9</i> rs12067569	1	55528629	G	A	A	0.04	0.05	0.36	0.04	0.06	1.00
<i>PCSK9</i> rs17111503	1	55503448	G	A	A	0.33	0.35	0.63	0.35	0.33	1.00
<i>PCSK9</i> rs2149041	1	55502137	G	C	C	0.36	0.37	1.00	0.39	0.37	1.00
<i>PCSK9</i> rs2182833	1	55500429	G	A	A	0.36	0.37	0.87	0.39	0.36	0.75
<i>PCSK9</i> rs2479406	1	55502672	C	A	C	0.06	0.05	0.39	0.04	0.07	1.00
<i>PCSK9</i> rs2479409	1	55504650	G	A	A	0.32	0.35	0.74	0.35	0.31	0.30
<i>PCSK9</i> rs2479410	1	55505861	G	A	A	0.11	0.12	0.08	0.14	0.11	0.48
<i>PCSK9</i> rs2483205	1	55518316	C	T	T	0.26	0.24	0.69	0.26	0.25	0.56
<i>PCSK9</i> rs2495482	1	55505732	G	A	A	0.06	0.05	1.00	0.06	0.06	1.00
<i>PCSK9</i> rs28385704	1	55506103	G	C	G	0.11	0.12	0.08	0.13	0.11	0.70
<i>PCSK9</i> rs41294819	1	55504586	G	A	G	0.12	0.12	0.08	0.13	0.12	0.48
<i>PCSK9</i> rs505151	1	55529187	G	A	G	0.04	0.05	0.36	0.04	0.06	1.00
<i>PCSK9</i> rs557435	1	55520864	G	A	A	0.05	0.06	0.53	0.04	0.07	0.56
<i>PCSK9</i> rs562556	1	55524237	G	A	G	0.01	0.01	1.00	0.01	0.01	1.00
<i>PCSK9</i> rs643257	1	55527918	C	T	C	0.01	0.01	1.00	0.01	0.01	1.00
<i>PCSK9</i> rs662145	1	55529828	C	T	C	0.10	0.11	0.46	0.12	0.11	1.00
<i>PCSK9</i> rs7523141	1	55498798	C	T	C	0.36	0.37	0.87	0.39	0.36	0.87
<i>PCSK9</i> rs7523242	1	55498949	C	T	C	0.36	0.37	0.87	0.40	0.37	0.75
<i>PCSK9</i> rs7525649	1	55499156	C	T	C	0.36	0.36	0.87	0.38	0.36	0.63
<i>PCSK9</i> rs7552841	1	55518752	C	T	T	0.14	0.18	0.31	0.15	0.14	0.22
<i>SCARB1</i> rs150222965	12	125299559	G	A	0	0.00	0.00	1.00	0.00	0.00	1.00
<i>SCARB1</i> rs3782287	12	125289265	G	A	A	0.29	0.27	0.26	0.29	0.29	0.59

<i>SCARB1</i> rs5888	12	125284748	G	A	A	0.24	0.26	0.12	0.24	0.24	1.00
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^a MAF, minor allele frequency in the sample; HWE, Hardy-Weinberg equilibrium.

Table S2 Association analysis of *APOE*, *PCSK9* haplotypes and the concentrations of HDL-c, LDL-c, ratio (LDL-c/HDL-c) in the maternal blood

Dependent variables	Haplotypes ^a	N(%) ^b	Unstandardized Coefficients B (95%CI) ^c	P-value	
Ratio (LDL-c/HDL-c)	<i>APOE</i>				
	C _{rs440446} G _{rs769450} T _{rs429358}	425 (68.77)	Ref.	Ref.	
	G _{rs440446} A _{rs769450} T _{rs429358}	138 (19.83)	0.14 (0.01, 0.26)	0.034	
	G _{rs440446} G _{rs769450} C _{rs429358}	83 (12.35)	0.17 (0.01, 0.33)	0.038	
	G _{rs440446} G _{rs769450} T _{rs429358}	70 (10.67)	0.08 (-0.09, 0.25)	0.333	
HDL-c	<i>APOE</i>				
	C _{rs440446} G _{rs769450} T _{rs429358}	425 (68.77)	Ref.	Ref.	
	G _{rs440446} A _{rs769450} T _{rs429358}	138 (19.83)	-0.07 (-0.16, 0.03)	0.181	
	G _{rs440446} G _{rs769450} C _{rs429358}	83 (12.35)	-0.07 (-0.19, 0.06)	0.299	
	G _{rs440446} G _{rs769450} T _{rs429358}	70 (10.67)	0.21 (0.07, 0.34)	0.003	
	<i>PCSK9</i>				
	G _{rs2479410} C _{rs11583723} C _{rs28385704}	635 (88.44)	Ref.	Ref.	
	A _{rs2479410} T _{rs11583723} G _{rs28385704}	84 (11.67)	-0.14 (-0.26, -0.01)	0.036	
	C _{rs7552841} G _{rs557435}	565 (82.60)	Ref.	Ref.	
	C _{rs7552841} A _{rs557435}	41 (5.84)	-0.05 (-0.21, 0.12)	0.591	
	T _{rs7552841} G _{rs557435}	114 (15.92)	0.13 (0.03, 0.24)	0.015	
	LDL-c	<i>APOE</i>			
		C _{rs440446} G _{rs769450} T _{rs429358}	425 (68.77)	Ref.	Ref.
		G _{rs440446} A _{rs769450} T _{rs429358}	138 (19.83)	0.14 (-0.07, 0.34)	0.194
G _{rs440446} G _{rs769450} C _{rs429358}		83 (12.35)	0.23 (-0.04, 0.50)	0.094	
G _{rs440446} G _{rs769450} T _{rs429358}		70 (10.67)	-0.23 (-0.52, 0.06)	0.124	
<i>PCSK9</i>					
G _{rs2479410} C _{rs11583723} C _{rs28385704}		635 (88.44)	Ref.	Ref.	
A _{rs2479410} T _{rs11583723} G _{rs28385704}		84 (11.67)	0.04 (-0.23, 0.31)	0.771	
C _{rs7552841} G _{rs557435}		565 (82.60)	Ref.	Ref.	
C _{rs7552841} A _{rs557435}		41 (5.84)	0.11 (-0.24, 0.46)	0.545	
T _{rs7552841} G _{rs557435}		114 (15.92)	0.12 (-0.11, 0.34)	0.309	

^a The haplotypes were analyzed as continues variables based on the number of corresponding haplotypes. The haplotype with the highest frequency was used as the reference haplotype. HDL-c, HDL-cholesterol; LDL-c, LDL-cholesterol; UV, umbilical venous.

^b The frequency of reference haplotype was calculated by dividing total number of reference haplotype by (2* the number of samples containing reference haplotype). The frequency of corresponding haplotype was calculated by dividing total number of corresponding haplotype by (2* the number of samples containing reference or corresponding haplotypes).

^c Unstandardized Coefficients B and 95% CIs were calculated by multiple linear regression adjusted by neonate sex, maternal age, pre-gestational BMI, parity number, gestational weight gain (GWG) and triglyceride level.

Table S3 Association analysis of *APOE*, *PCSK9*, *LPL* haplotypes and the concentrations of HDL-c, LDL-c, ratio (LDL-c/HDL-c) in the UV blood

Dependent variables	Haplotypes ^a	N(%) ^b	Unstandardized Coefficients (95%CI) ^c	P-value
Ratio (LDL-c/HDL-c)	<i>PCSK9</i>			
	G _{rs2479409} G _{rs2495482} G _{rs2479410} C _{rs11583723} C _{rs28385704}	375(74.70)	Ref.	Ref.
	A _{rs2479409} G _{rs2495482} A _{rs2479410} T _{rs11583723} G _{rs28385704}	26(4.76)	0.25 (0.03, 0.47)	0.025
	A _{rs2479409} G _{rs2495482} G _{rs2479410} C _{rs11583723} C _{rs28385704}	208(29.46)	0.06 (-0.06, 0.17)	0.341
	G _{rs2479409} A _{rs2495482} G _{rs2479410} C _{rs11583723} C _{rs28385704}	43(8.24)	0.05 (-0.16, 0.26)	0.643
HDL-c	<i>APOE</i>			
	C _{rs157582} C _{rs440446} G _{rs769450} T _{rs429358}	436(71.48)	Ref.	Ref.
	C _{rs157582} G _{rs440446} A _{rs769450} T _{rs429358}	139(19.86)	-0.08 (-0.18, 0.02)	0.106
	C _{rs157582} G _{rs440446} G _{rs769450} T _{rs429358}	24(3.82)	0.06 (-0.14, 0.26)	0.552
	T _{rs157582} G _{rs440446} G _{rs769450} C _{rs429358}	63(9.78)	0.06 (-0.08, 0.21)	0.393
	T _{rs157582} G _{rs440446} G _{rs769450} T _{rs429358}	40(6.29)	0.19 (0.03, 0.36)	0.021
	<i>LPL</i>			
	C _{rs263} C _{rs283}	438(72.04)	Ref.	Ref.
	C _{rs263} T _{rs283}	126(18.42)	0.01 (-0.09, 0.11)	0.815
	T _{rs263} C _{rs283}	154(22.06)	0.12 (0.02, 0.21)	0.014
	C _{rs283} T _{rs320} A _{rs326} C _{rs328} A _{rs12678919} T _{rs4406409}	446(71.94)	Ref.	Ref.
	C _{rs283} G _{rs320} G _{rs326} C _{rs328} A _{rs12678919} C _{rs4406409}	73(10.99)	0.13 (0.00, 0.26)	0.045
	C _{rs283} G _{rs320} G _{rs326} G _{rs328} G _{rs12678919} C _{rs4406409}	69(10.33)	0.10 (-0.03, 0.23)	0.143
	T _{rs283} T _{rs320} A _{rs326} C _{rs328} A _{rs12678919} T _{rs4406409}	126(18.31)	0.01 (-0.09, 0.11)	0.829
	<i>PCSK9</i>			
	T _{rs7523141} T _{rs7523242} T _{rs7525649} G _{rs2182833}	443(70.99)	Ref.	Ref.
	T _{rs10788994} G _{rs2149041} A _{rs2479406}			
	C _{rs7523141} C _{rs7523242} C _{rs7525649} A _{rs2182833}	227(31.70)	0.03 (-0.06, 0.11)	0.564
	C _{rs10788994} C _{rs2149041} A _{rs2479406}			
	C _{rs7523141} C _{rs7523242} C _{rs7525649} A _{rs2182833}	38(5.90)	-0.07 (-0.25, 0.10)	0.418
	C _{rs10788994} C _{rs2149041} C _{rs2479406}			
	G _{rs2479409} G _{rs2495482} G _{rs2479410} C _{rs11583723} C _{rs28385704}	375(74.70)	Ref.	Ref.
	A _{rs2479409} G _{rs2495482} A _{rs2479410} T _{rs11583723} G _{rs28385704}	26(4.76)	0.00 (-0.19, 0.19)	0.997
	A _{rs2479409} G _{rs2495482} G _{rs2479410} C _{rs11583723} C _{rs28385704}	208(29.46)	0.04 (-0.05, 0.14)	0.358
	G _{rs2479409} A _{rs2495482} G _{rs2479410} C _{rs11583723} C _{rs28385704}	43(8.24)	0.06 (-0.12, 0.24)	0.504
LDL-c	<i>APOE</i>			
	C _{rs157582} C _{rs440446} G _{rs769450} T _{rs429358}	436(71.48)	Ref.	Ref.
	C _{rs157582} G _{rs440446} A _{rs769450} T _{rs429358}	139(19.86)	0.05 (-0.17, 0.26)	0.677
	C _{rs157582} G _{rs440446} G _{rs769450} T _{rs429358}	24(3.82)	0.02 (-0.41, 0.46)	0.916
	T _{rs157582} G _{rs440446} G _{rs769450} C _{rs429358}	63(9.78)	0.20 (-0.11, 0.50)	0.215
	T _{rs157582} G _{rs440446} G _{rs769450} T _{rs429358}	40(6.29)	0.45 (0.10, 0.80)	0.014
	<i>LPL</i>			

	C _{rs263} C _{rs283}	438(72.04)		Ref.	Ref.
	C _{rs263} T _{rs283}	126(18.42)	-0.03 (-0.25, 0.19)		0.792
	T _{rs263} C _{rs283}	154(22.06)	0.39 (0.20, 0.59)		<0.001
	C _{rs283} T _{rs320} A _{rs326} C _{rs328} A _{rs12678919} T _{rs4406409}	446(71.94)		Ref.	Ref.
	C _{rs283} G _{rs320} G _{rs326} C _{rs328} A _{rs12678919} C _{rs4406409}	73(10.99)	0.37 (0.10, 0.65)		0.009
	C _{rs283} G _{rs320} G _{rs326} G _{rs328} G _{rs12678919} C _{rs4406409}	69(10.33)	0.23 (-0.05, 0.51)		0.105
	T _{rs283} T _{rs320} A _{rs326} C _{rs328} A _{rs12678919} T _{rs4406409}	126(18.31)	-0.05 (-0.27, 0.17)		0.646
<i>PCSK9</i>					
	T _{rs7523141} T _{rs7523242} T _{rs7525649} G _{rs2182833}	443(70.99)		Ref.	Ref.
	T _{rs10788994} G _{rs2149041} A _{rs2479406}				
	C _{rs7523141} C _{rs7523242} C _{rs7525649} A _{rs2182833}	227(31.70)	0.18 (0.01, 0.36)		0.042
	C _{rs10788994} C _{rs2149041} A _{rs2479406}				
	C _{rs7523141} C _{rs7523242} C _{rs7525649} A _{rs2182833}	38(5.90)	-0.11 (-0.48, 0.26)		0.570
	C _{rs10788994} C _{rs2149041} C _{rs2479406}				
	G _{rs2479409} G _{rs2495482} G _{rs2479410} C _{rs11583723} C _{rs28385704}	375(74.70)		Ref.	Ref.
	A _{rs2479409} G _{rs2495482} A _{rs2479410} T _{rs11583723} G _{rs28385704}	26(4.76)	0.47 (0.09, 0.86)		0.017
	A _{rs2479409} G _{rs2495482} G _{rs2479410} C _{rs11583723} C _{rs28385704}	208(29.46)	0.17 (-0.03, 0.36)		0.093
	G _{rs2479409} A _{rs2495482} G _{rs2479410} C _{rs11583723} C _{rs28385704}	43(8.24)	0.12 (-0.25, 0.49)		0.517

^a The haplotypes were analyzed as continuous variables based on the number of corresponding haplotypes. The haplotype with the highest frequency was used as the reference haplotype. HDL-c, HDL-cholesterol; LDL-c, LDL-cholesterol; UV, umbilical venous.

^b The frequency of reference haplotype was calculated by dividing total number of reference haplotype by (2* the number of samples containing reference haplotype). The frequency of corresponding haplotype was calculated by dividing total number of corresponding haplotype by (2* the number of samples containing reference or corresponding haplotypes).

^c Unstandardized Coefficients B and 95% CIs were calculated by multiple linear regression adjusted by neonate sex, maternal age, pre-gestational BMI, parity number, gestational weight gain (GWG) and triglyceride level.